

In its simplest example: $27^5 + 84^5 + 110^5 + 133^5 = 144^5$, A *Counterexample to Euler's Sum of Powers Conjecture* (Lander & Parkin, 1966) is not a counter example to Euler's Sum of Powers Conjecture which states, "for all integers n and k greater than 1, if the sum of n kth powers of positive integers is itself a kth power, then n is greater than or equal to k." (Weisstein, 2020)

$$A_{n_1}^k + A_{n_2}^k + \dots = B^k$$

$$27^5 + 84^5 + 110^5 + 133^5 = 144^5$$

$$(3^3)^5 + 84^5 + 110^5 + 133^5 = (12^2)^5$$

$$(A^3)^5 + 84^5 + 110^5 + 133^5 = (12^2)^5$$

$$(A^3)^5 + (21B^2)^5 + C^5 + C^5 = (18D^3)^5$$

The first, second, and last term do not represent an integer, but rather a system. The result is an early prediction of Fractal Geometry that computers would later help us to discover. A point looks like a point until you zoom in and discover it is a repeating pattern as seen in figure 1 below. (Mandelbrot, 2020)

References

- Lander, L., & Parkin, T. (1966). Counterexample to Euler's conjecture on sums of like powers. *Bull. Amer. Math. Soc* 72, 1079.
- Mandelbrot, B. B. (2020, March 17). *Fractals and the Geometry of Nature*. Retrieved from math.yale.edu: https://users.math.yale.edu/~bbm3/web_pdfs/encyclopediaBritannica.pdf
- Weisstein, E. W. (2020, March 15). *Euler's Sum of Powers Conjecture*. Retrieved from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource: <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/EulersSumofPowersConjecture.html>